

Supplementary material

“The HURRIER Process for Experimentation in Business-to-Business Mission-Critical Systems” David Issa Mattos, Anas Dakkak, Jan Bosch and Helena Holmström Olsson

RQ1: What are the types of experiments that are conducted in Ericsson and that are relevant in the development of mission-critical B2B systems?

RQ2: What are the current continuous experimentation practices used at Ericsson in the development of mission-critical B2B systems?

RQ3: Can the HURRIER process can be used to drive CE in mission-critical B2B systems at Ericsson?

RQ4: What are the current CE challenges and opportunities in mission-critical B2B systems observed at Ericsson?

Interview guide 1

For first interview.

General information

- Role
- Years of experience
- Years in the company
- (Clarification of what the term experimentation refers in the context of this study)
- Do you any experience running field experiments?

Experimentation process and general overview

For people and teams that were involved in a specific experimentation

- Which type of product did you use experimentation? [RQ1]
- What is the feature in our own words? [RQ1]
- How critical is the system? [RQ1]
 - And how does this (criticality) influence the experiment design?
- How this idea came from? [RQ1]
 - What were the decisions made you (team) choose this design? [RQ2/RQ3]
 - What are the restrictions to run this experiment? Disadvantages? [RQ4]
 - Technical (technology)
 - Organizational (people to approve, agree, communicate the results)
 - Business (the customers)
 - Does the type of feature change these restrictions?
- Can you summarize the development process with the experiment? [RQ1/RQ2]
 - What were the development milestones? [RQ3]
 - Passing all tests? customer approval? Deployment? Gradual rollout? A/B testing? [RQ3]

- How was the customer involved in this process and in these milestones? [RQ3]
- What was the end goal of the experiment? [RQ1]
 - Get data more from the customer environment to support development?
 - Create new regression tests for the system?
 - See how it performs with customer specific metrics?
 - Validation of the solution?
- How did experimentation change the requirements specification? [RQ1/RQ4]
 - Did it relax it a bit?
 - Or did it just add more requirements on top of that?
- What were the product/architecture characteristics that allow you to run this experiment? [RQ1/RQ2/RQ3]
- How did it go? How do the development perceived this process?
 - What were the advantages of running this (specific) experiment compare to the traditional process?
(Traditional: long dev cycle + testing + verification)
 - Faster? Cheaper?
 - More stressful?
 - Did it increase some burden because you (team) needed to communicate with the customers directly?

Customer aspects

For customer-facing interviewees

- How did you select a customer to run the experiment? [RQ3/RQ4]
- What factors played an important role in this decision? [RQ3/RQ4]
- Any other beyond technical aspects? [RQ3/RQ4]
- How is data being collected for experiments? [RQ3/RQ4]
 - Does the R&D get everything they need from the configuration/data points or does it need more from the customers?
- When/How the customers try to scope down the experiment/ data collection? [RQ3/RQ4]

Specific experimentation techniques

Clarifications when a specific experimentation was mentioned

- Can you describe (if not explained) this technique? [RQ1/RQ2]
 - What is the main goal?
 - How do you measure if it was successful?
 - Have you use this technique before?

Dark/Passive launches

- What are the criteria to plan/develop/use a passive deployment (dark launches)? [RQ2]
 - How often have you/others done dark launches?
 - How do you utilize the data from dark launches?
- What are the criteria to determine if the dark launch was successful? [RQ2]
 - How many data points or confidence level do you need?
 - Same performance, better performance?

- Do you run any statistical comparison between the two (existing + dark launch)? [RQ2]
- Do you need customer approval if it is a dark launch? [RQ4]

A/B testing and time series

- How do you analyze the metrics? [RQ2]
 - Do you look how the metrics move with time?
 - Is it important just the average of the metrics or does it matter how it moves and changes with time?
 - Do weekends/weekdays have same weight on experiments?
- Have you run an experiment with this feature in only selected users, to see how they compare with the other users? E.g. did they use more, improved metrics etc? [RQ2]
- What are the conditions that this would work at Ericsson? [RQ3/RQ4]

Release techniques

- How are these types of deployments planned? [RQ2]
 - Feature toggles?
 - Traffic routing?
 - Manual deployments
- How likely is the customer willing to do a field experiment for innovation? What are the restrictions imposed by the customers? [RQ2/RQ4]
- Are those restrictions only for metrics? i.e. are metrics performance what the customer cares most? [RQ2/RQ4]
- Perception of team on these passive deployments? [RQ4]
- Does it affect the pressure, engagement of the team [RQ4]

Experiments for innovation (from prototyping)

- What is the process from an internal idea to become an actual customer deployment? [RQ1/RQ2]
- How long does it take?
- Who needs to approve internally? [RQ2]
 - Does the customer need to approve as well?
- How much does it change from the original concept? [RQ1/RQ2/RQ3]
- Do these ideas come from more research/innovation focused groups or could they come from different product development groups? [RQ1]
- How does this process of experimenting with stable and legacy systems work for innovation? [RQ3]
 - Are there any advantages over the continuous deployment product?
 - Can you easily move an innovation feature from legacy systems to a new system?
- If an experiment is successful, how does it transfer to other products [RQ3]
- How are successful prototypes transferred to other development teams? [RQ1]
 - In the form of specific requirements?

Data collection for experiments. For people working with data collection

- Describe a little bit what is your work? [RQ3]
- What are the challenges in collecting data for experiments? [RQ4]

- How does collecting and aggregating data from different countries and customers work? [RQ4]
- Is the data from a customer comparable to the other customer? [RQ4]
- Do customers impose restrictions in the data collection? [RQ4]

Interview Guide 2

For follow-up interviews.

Last time we discussed we talked about the steps/process used in the planning an experiment

Perception and changes

- What was your perception was this process after this experiment? [RQ3/RQ4]
- What was positive? What was negative? [RQ3/RQ4]
- What was challenging from this process? [RQ3/RQ4]
- What would you have changed on this process? [RQ3/RQ4]
- Was there any step missing that you would add? [RQ3/RQ4]

Customer involvement

- How was the customer collaboration in this process? [RQ3/RQ4]
 - Did they see it as something good that you should continue to do?
- Was there any misunderstanding about the goals of each of the process with the customer? [RQ3/RQ4]
 - Maybe they were expecting different results in each step

Speed

- Do you think this feature development was faster with this closer customer collaboration? [RQ3/RQ4]
- What would you change to make it even faster? (In terms of the process, not the complexity of the feature itself) [RQ3/RQ4]
 - More frequent and smaller deployments?
 - More syncing with customer?
 - More support from internal testing and labs to catch up earlier some problems observed in the customer network?

Internal testing and validation

- Could the internal testing be improved to catch up problems earlier on? [RQ3/RQ4]
- Was there any case observed from the field with the customer network that could be brought back to improve internal testing? [RQ3/RQ4]